

Yield of Ruchi in All India Coordinated trials, state trials, local verification trials, farmer's field, and maximization demonstrations.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)							
	All India Coordinated Trials				State trials ^e	LVT ^f	Farmer's field ^g	Maximization demonstration ^h
	1986 ^a	1087 ^b	1988 ^c	1989 ^d				
Ruchi	5.2	4.0	4.7	5.2	3.9	6.0	5.2	8.7
Jaya	5.3	3.8	4.4	4.7	3.3	—	—	—
Local check	4.9	3.8	4.5	4.6	3.4	5.3	4.3	—

^a Av over 13 locations. ^b Av over 12 locations. ^c Av over 15 locations. ^d Av over 4 locations. ^e Av over 6 yr, 19 trials, 4 locations. ^f Av over 2 yr, 6 locations. ^g Av over 30 farmers' fields of 0.4 ha. ^h Av over 2 yr.

semitall (105 cm ± 10 cm) and, when direct seeded, can compete well with

weeds at the early vegetative phase. Grain yield averages 5-6 t/ha (see table).

Integrated germplasm improvement – upland

Evaluation of early rice genotypes for upland conditions in rolling fields of Karnataka, India

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We evaluated 25 short-duration rice genotypes (<125 d) during rainy season (May-Nov) 1987-89. The area (15°-50' N, 74°-40' E, and 697 m above sea level) has rolling fields that retain moisture for 3 to 3 1/2 mo during the normal cropping season. Annual precipitation averages about 950 mm. Total precipitation during the three cropping seasons of the experiment was 738.0, 1,034.3, and 607.3 mm,

respectively. Soil is a silty clay loam, with pH 6.3, 0.75% organic C, 9 kg P/ha, and 170 kg K/ha.

Rice was drilled in 20-cm rows at 100 kg seed/ha. The crop was fertilized with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

IET7991-11-2 and CR544-1-5 matured about 17 d earlier than high-

It matures in 130 d, is nonlodging even under high fertility because of its thick culms, and suits the rainfed lowland conditions of the state.

Ruchi grain is long, bold 35 g/1,000 grains, and suitable for puffed rice. It registered 4th in All India Coordinated trials in 1986 and first in 1989.

Ruchi may replace medium-duration, high-yielding varieties like IR8, Jaya, Pragati, and Phalgun, and has been recommended for release in 1990. ■

yielding local check Rasi (IET1444) (see table). Neela matured about 10 d earlier. These three genotypes significantly outyielded other early genotypes, and yielded as high as the local check.

In view of their earliness, IET7991-11-2 and Neela have been recommended for multilocation trials. CR544-1-5 was not considered because its grain tends to shatter when harvest is delayed. ■

Grain yield and plant characters^a of a few early rice genotypes under rainfed conditions in Mugad, Karnataka, India.

Genotype	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicles/m ² (no.)	Duration (d)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET7991-11-2	74.1	17.9	321.5	101	3.7
CR544-1-5	74.9	19.7	241.5	102	3.3
Neela	62.0	20.2	307.3	108	3.2
Rasi (IET1444) (local check)	79.7	18.2	250.0	118	3.1
LSD (0.05)	7.1	7.8	75.5	4.0	0.9
CV (%)	6.1	20.0	11.3	3.1	1.5

^aAv of 1987, 1988, and 1989 rainy seasons.

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Fertilizer management

Impact of nursery nutrients on growth and yield of rice crop

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Nursery management is an important factor in crop production. In very thickly populated nurseries, plant roots spread

out on the soil surface and intensively exploit soil fertility. If soil fertility is low, seedlings will be thin and pale. A considerable amount of the nursery may be spoiled during pulling.

We studied the use of N and P by the rice nursery and the impact of nursery nutrition on the subsequent crop in a field experiment at Saraimiara farm. Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam,

Table 1. Effect of fertilizer applied to nursery on growth parameters of 25-d-old rice seedlings.^a

Seedling treatment	Leaves/plant (no.)	Height (cm)	100-seedling weight (g)	N content (%)	P content (%)
No N	3.8	19.2	65	1.86	0.251
100 kg N/ha	4.7	30.4	152	2.28	0.258
200 kg N/ha	5.1	31.9	243	2.34	0.312
No P	4.8	30.8	141	2.08	0.323
21.5 kg P/ha	5.0	31.3	153	2.12	0.338
43.0 kg P/ha	5.3	31.7	166	2.15	0.345
LSD (0.05)	0.3	1.01	20	0.04	0.005

^a 2 yr pooled data.